

THERAPEUTIC EFFECT OF OLIVE OIL ON THE WALL OF HEART VENTRICLES DAMAGED BY ALCOHOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884217>

According to the World Health Organization, 1.5 million people die from alcoholism every year.

Current experiments show that the effectiveness of treatment of cardiovascular diseases using phytotherapy and chemical means is much higher. Furthermore olive oil is of special importance in preventing cardiovascular diseases. This is due to the fact that olive oil reduces the amount of unsaturated fatty acids in the blood, reduces the oxidation of fats, and increases the sensitivity of insulin receptors. At the same time, it has a blood-thinning, endothelium-strengthening, blood-pressure-lowering and anti-inflammatory effect, either directly or by influencing the oxidation process. At the same time, it prevents heart remodeling and diabetes.

Purpose of the study: Histological study of the heart of rats poisoned with alcohol and detoxified with olive oil.

Research materials and methods. Experimental studies were carried out on twelve-month-old rats. The rats were divided into three groups: control, experimental and correctional group. Histological samples were prepared from the wall of the left ventricle of the rat heart and studied.

Results. The results of histological examinations showed that the thickness of the epicardial layer of the left ventricular wall of the heart in twelve-month detoxification of rats poisoned with ethyl alcohol ranged from 36.82 to 39.83 mcm, with an average of 38.69 ± 0.25 mcm. Also, the thickness of the outer plate of the epicardial layer is from 12.27 to 13.28 mcm, with an average of 12.90 ± 0.08 mcm, and the inner plate is from 24.55 to 26.55 mcm, with an average of 25.79 ± 0.16 mcm.

During this period of rat correction, the thickness of the left ventricular myocardial layer was found to be 3045.20 to 3293.60 mcm, with an average of 3199.65 ± 20.37 mcm.

The thickness of the endocardial layer of the left ventricular wall ranges from 57.81 to 62.53 mcm, with an average of 60.74 ± 0.39 mcm. At the same time, the thickness of the endothelial layer of the endocardium was from 24.09 to 26.05 mcm, with an average of 25.31 ± 0.16 mcm, and the subendothelial

layer was from 33.72 to 36.47 mcm, with an average of 35.43 ± 0.23 consisted of mcm.

In twelve-month-old rats, the thickness of the epicardial layer of the wall of the right ventricle of the heart ranges from 31.00 to 45.85 mcm, with an average of 40.16 ± 1.22 mcm. Also, the thickness of the outer plate of the epicardial layer is from 7.75 to 11.46 mcm, with an average of 10.04 ± 0.30 mcm, and the inner plate is from 23.767 to 35.15 mcm, with an average of 30.79 ± 0.93 mcm. did

During this period of rat detoxification, the thickness of the right ventricular myocardium layer was found to be from 1210.72 to 1407.60 mcm, with an average of 1310.54 ± 16.14 mcm.

The thickness of the endocardial layer of the right ventricular wall ranges from 54.03 to 62.81 mcm, with an average of 58.38 ± 0.72 mcm. At the same time, the thickness of the endothelial layer of the endocardium is from 13.50 to 15.70 mcm, the average is 14.60 ± 0.18 mcm, the subendothelial layer is from 40.52 to 47.11 mcm, the average is 43.79 ± 0.54 consisted of mcm.

Conclusion. In an experimental experiment, it was found that as a result of alcohol poisoning, all layers of the wall of the heart ventricles are thinned, and as a result of correction with olive oil, these changes are partially restored.

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